

**Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 3**

**Report on the Online Training Courses
Deliverable D5.5**

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

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ESiWACE is on Zenodo, the Open Access repository for scientific results

<https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>

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1. Abstract /publishable summary

Two live online training courses have been run as part of ESiWACE3. The first of these covered the use of the ESiWACE-developed tool Kernel Tuner, and the second the software profiling tools Extrae and Paraver. Since these tools have general applicability for the HPC community beyond ESiWACE3's core weather and climate modelling target audience, advantage was taken of the Training Sprint initiative implemented by the CASTIEL2 Training Working Group to organise the courses in collaboration with Euro CC Austria, ESiWACE3's paired national competence centre, thus allowing us to promote the exploitation of the tools beyond ESiWACE3's core weather and climate modelling target audience. In addition, a hybrid in-person and online training session covering use of the containerised version of the earth system model EC-Earth4, developed in ESiWACE3 Task 1.4, has been held. Lecture materials from all of the sessions have been made openly available online.

2. Conclusion & Results

The two online training courses on ESiWACE3 software development tools arranged in partnership with Euro CC Austria each attracted large, broad-based audiences, 33 and 36 participants respectively (ESiWACE3's KPI for the courses is 20). Participants represented a range of domains, as well as career groups. We conclude that partnering with the NCC for these courses brought benefit in terms of helping to extend dissemination and potential exploitation of ESiWACE3 tools. The training session on the containerised EC-Earth was of necessity more tightly focused on ESiWACE3's core domain group.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to achieving all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Grant Agreement:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
A1: Transfer and establish knowledge and technology for efficient and scalable simulations of weather and climate across the Earth system modelling community in Europe.	Yes
A2: Close common technology gaps in the knowledge and toolbox for high-resolution Earth system modelling via joint developments across the European community.	Yes
A3: Serve as a sustainable community hub for training, communication, and dissemination for high-performance computing for weather and climate modelling in Europe.	Yes

Specific goals in the work plan	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1: Increase efficiency of weather and climate simulations on state-of-the-art supercomputers.	Yes
O2: Design tools to close technology gaps for high performance computing.	No
O3: Develop tools to tackle the data challenge of high-resolution weather and climate modelling.	Yes
O4: Support the wider community of weather and climate modelling in the use of state-of-the-art supercomputers via targeted services.	No
O5: Support the wider community of weather and climate modelling in the use of state-of-the-art supercomputers via training and capacity building.	Yes

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O6: Build a well-connected and inclusive community for high-resolution Earth system modelling across Earth system science and HPC and establish connections and knowledge transfer between existing European initiatives.	Yes
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4. Detailed report on the deliverable

4.1. Kernel Tuner

Kernel Tuner¹ is a software development tool for the creation of highly-optimised and tuned GPU applications. Developed over some years by ESiWACE3 partner the Netherlands e-Science Center, it has been expanded as part of ESiWACE3 Task 2.3. It provided the basis for the first ESiWACE3 online training course, an interactive workshop on GPU optimisation held over two half days on 12 and 13 September 2024 and reported in Milestone M5.4 (ESiWACE3 M5.4, 2025).

4.2. Extrae and Paraver

The second online training course, which took place on 27 January 2025, covered the use of two performance analysis tools aimed at supporting developers in the evaluation, tuning and optimisation of their codes: Extrae, which is designed to generate trace files for a post-mortem analysis without modifying the source code, and Paraver, which is a flexible performance analyser of the Extrae traces. The tutorial consisted of a theoretical part followed by a hands-on section where participants were able to practise analysing an Extrae trace with Paraver. The teaching example was drawn from a climate application, but the applicability of the tools to any HPC domain was emphasised.

Once again, the course was held in conjunction with Euro CC Austria, who advertised the event across their networks, handled registration and provided access to computing resources on the Vienna Scientific Cluster 5. For ESiWACE 3, the training was led by Mario Acosta, Víctor Correal, Carlos Peña and Xavier Yepes-Arbós of the Barcelona Supercomputing Center. The programme was as follows:

- 9:10 - Profiling analysis with BSC tools: theory and weather and climate applications examples
- 10:15 - Coffee break
- 10:30 - Introduction to the Extrae tool: practical case
- 11:30 - Introduction to the Paraver tool: practical case
- 12:30 - Lunch break
- 13:30 - Analysis of a real application using Paraver
- 15:00 - Coffee break
- 15:15 - Analysis of a real application using Paraver (continuation)
- 16:15 - Q&A
- 16:30 - End

The introduction to Extrae covered how Extrae works, loading and setting up the required environment using EESSI (the European Environment for Scientific Software Installations), generation of the necessary configuration files and interpretation of the resultant trace files. It was followed by a practical exercise. The introduction to Paraver covered the basic functionalities of Paraver with plenty of

¹ https://kerneltuner.github.io/kernel_tuner/stable/

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examples of output. Use of the tool was then illustrated using an example generated from the regional weather and climate model Harmonie-AROME. Materials from the course are available online at https://gitlab.earth.bsc.es/vcorreal/extrae-paraver-training/-/blob/main/ESiWACE3_%20BSC%20tools%20hands-on%20for%20NCC%20Austria.pdf?ref_type=heads.

Both ESiWACE3 and Euro CC Austria advertised the course on their respective websites and through their mailing lists and social media. 36 participants attended, of whom 17% were female. The largest career group represented was research and development staff (14), while 12 could be described as early career scientists (post-doc or student) and the remainder comprised teaching, admin or support staff. The geographic spread across Europe was broad, and included representation from ITC countries Bulgaria, Croatia, the Czech Republic, Greece, Lithuania, Montenegro and Türkiye. As with the first course on Kernel Tuner, our experience was that the partnership with Euro CC Austria helped us to reach audiences beyond our existing contact base.

4.3. EC-Earth4 in a container

In contrast to the two earlier courses, the training organised by ESiWACE3 on use of the containerised version of the earth system model EC-Earth4 (see ESiWACE3 Deliverable D1.5, 2024) was aimed very much at the climate modelling community. For licensing reasons, access to the container is expected to be limited to members of the EC-Earth consortium, so the decision was taken to arrange the training on 11 June 2026 within the context of the 2026 EC-Earth general assembly, which was held as a hybrid online/ in-person event. In doing so, we aimed to achieve maximum visibility amongst all members of the consortium, which with around 40 institutional members extends well beyond the ESiWACE3 consortium and its regular partners.

The training was presented by Joakim Kjellsson of the Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute. A theoretical introduction covering the rationale for the use of containers, choice of container platform and method for building a container was followed by a hands-on practical involving use of the containerised EC-Earth4. Notwithstanding the focus of the session on users and potential users of EC-Earth, we expect the introductory material on the rationale for the use of containers to be of more general interest, and have made the lecture notes available in Zenodo²

15 participants attended, a mix of postdoc or other early-career researchers and more experienced researchers. From those who completed the feedback questionnaire the response was universally positive, with all awarding a rating of at least 8 out of 10 and three quarters giving 9. Respondents found the course well balanced and praised the clarity of the step-by-step instructions and the trainer's knowledge of the subject.

5. References

ESiWACE3 M5.4. (2025). *First online training course - Milestone M5.4*.
<https://zenodo.org/records/17897075>.

ESiWACE3 D1.5. (2024). *Report on the containerisation of EC-Earth 4 - Deliverable 1.5*.
<https://zenodo.org/records/13827671>

² <https://zenodo.org/records/20727386>

6. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered

At the point the project began, we had envisaged advertising and promoting the online courses through ESiWACE3's network of contacts and social media. The later emergence of the Training Sprint set up by the CASTIEL2 training working group, in which ESiWACE3 representative Nikki Brown participated, opened up an opportunity to extend the audiences for the courses beyond the core target group for ESiWACE3 to those working in other domains for which the tools could be of value.

7. How this deliverable contributes to the EuroHPC strategy

Delivering high quality training on tools developed within ESiWACE3 contributes to the EuroHPC strategy by promulgating awareness of and confidence in the use of tools which can be of value to a wide range of HPC users.

8. Sustainability

Materials from all of the events have been published online and are available to support self-study.

9. Community engagement, dissemination, and exploitation

9.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Grant Agreement, the audience for this deliverable is:

X	The general public (PU).
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This report is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

Materials are openly available through the ESiWACE3 website.

9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo Link	Estimated number of persons reached
This deliverable is itself a report of dissemination activities.					

9.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

In preparation OR submitted?	Title	All authors	Title of the periodical or the series	Is/Will <i>open access</i> be provided to this publication?
N/A				

9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

None.